

Tribological and corrosion properties of β -TiNb alloy modified by plasma electrolytic oxidation: Evaluation of the synergistic effect of composition and processing time through statistical evaluation

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ABSTRACT

For bone implants, β -titanium alloy is promising mainly due to its low modulus of elasticity; the disadvantage may be the insufficient wear-resistant and corrosion-resistant properties. Bulk β -Ti39Nb alloy and magnetron sputtered β -Ti39Nb alloy were surface modified by micro-arc oxidation (MAO) technique in an alkaline solution. The aim was to define in detail the relationships between the chemical composition of the surfaces, their morphology, and the tribological and corrosion properties. The structural properties, phase and chemical composition of the coating, tribological and corrosion properties were studied in detail using SEM, EDX, XRD, XPS and EDX analysis. The particles released during tribological measurements were evaluated using SEM/EDX particle analysis followed by statistical treatment of the particle parameters (material, size, area) using multiple factor analysis and principal component analysis. The results show that increased wear resistance was achieved for both magnetron-sputtered layers and bulk materials. The friction coefficient for the MAO- Al_2O_3 friction pair samples ranged from 0.5 to 0.6 in phosphate-buffered solution. For powder metallurgy-prepared bulk β -Ti39Nb, MAO represents an effective tool to reduce the high friction coefficient from 1.0 to 1.1 to values of 0.4–0.5. The results of the particle analysis confirm that with increasing MAO process time, there is an increase in the number of released particles with increased Si content, which correlates well with the results of tribological tests. The evaluated tribological parameters wear rate, track width, and the chemical elements Si and Ti have a significant weak positive correlation, confirming that the presence of these elements in MAO coatings affects the resulting tribological parameters. Multivariate analysis revealed the greatest correlation of the resulting particle composition with the tribological attributes and original material and, to a lesser extent, with the process time.

1. Introduction

Several industrial techniques have been developed to enable the deposition of bioactive surfaces to achieve better key implant surface properties of the most commonly used ($\alpha + \beta$) Ti-6Al-4 V alloys, which are a prerequisite for successful osteointegration of orthopaedic and dental implants. However, despite being the most widely used, these

biomaterials do not achieve the required mechanical, corrosion and especially tribological properties [1]. Therefore, in the last two decades, the development in the field of biomedical metallic materials has been oriented towards manufacturing β -titanium alloys stabilised by Nb, Ta, and Mo, leading to better biomechanical and corrosion properties than those of commercially available α and $\alpha + \beta$ titanium alloys [2]. Furthermore, the β -titanium alloys prepared in this way do not contain

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toxic elements as in Ti-6Al-4 V alloy; however, for biomedical applications, it is necessary to choose a suitable surface treatment due to low abrasion and corrosion resistance [3].

Surface modification of titanium alloys can be achieved using a range of conventional and non-conventional technologies, including anodisation [4], laser cladding technology [5], plasma spraying [6], physical vapour deposition (PVD) and chemical vapour deposition (CVD) technologies [7], nitriding [8], micro-arc oxidation (MAO) [9], high-velocity oxygen fuel spray (HVOF) [10]. To achieve better adhesion, biocompatibility, abrasion or corrosion resistance of the coating, a combination of multiple coating methods is used to prepare duplex or also hybrid coatings [11]. In one study [12], a ZrTi oxide coating was prepared using a combination of PVD and MAO techniques, which led to better corrosion resistance, significantly lower friction coefficient and increased osteogenic differentiation compared to the substrate (Ti-6Al-4 V). In this context, the application of β -titanium alloy stabilised by Nb is proposed as a non-toxic, biocompatible material [13]. The deposition of β -Ti39Nb using the PVD technique allows the formation of a chemically stable, adhesive layer that forms a diffusion barrier and, thus, prevents the release of toxic metals from the Ti-6Al-4 V substrate volume to the surface [14].

A key parameter ensuring increased integration of implants with bone is its surface structure, which can be effectively influenced using MAO technology to achieve an abrasion-resistant surface that allows increased osseointegration and reduction of micromotions [15]. In the case of β -Ti39Nb alloy, a CaP MAO coating with high porosity and a thickness of 40–70 μm was successfully deposited [16]. Songur et al. [17] found that the MAO surface treatment of a novel β -titanium alloy Ti-29Nb-13Ta-4.6Zr led to better corrosion properties than the untreated surface, notably a reduction in the corrosion rate up to 14 times. MAO coating was also prepared on β -alloy Ti-39Nb-6Zr in alkaline electrolyte using KOH, which led to a significant improvement of corrosion parameters (electrochemical impedance, corrosion current density, corrosion potential) too. Thus it can be concluded that the MAO process allows the preparation of corrosion-resistant coatings [18]. Tribological properties of the β -titanium alloy were studied by Habazaki et al. [19], who confirmed the use of alkaline electrolyte in the preparation of wear-resistant MAO coating. The application of biomedical coatings or a suitable combination of these coatings is used to increase the durability of implants. By combining PVD and MAO technologies, increased corrosion and wear resistance can be achieved.

Since there is an increasing interest in the use of β -titanium alloy in the field of bone implants, this study is focused on describing the relationships between the chemical composition of the surfaces, its morphology and tribological and corrosion properties. In the present study, the deposited PVD layers of β -titanium alloy Ti39Nb (61 wt% Ti, 39 wt% Nb), which were subsequently oxidised by MAO technology in an alkaline solution, were evaluated in detail using chemical and physical techniques. The oxide layers prepared on substrates of cast Ti-6Al-4 V alloy and Ti39Nb alloy prepared by powder metallurgy were evaluated in terms of corrosion resistance and tribological properties in physiological solutions. The tribological properties of the modified surfaces were studied in detail, including a description of the nature of the particles formed during abrasion of the β -titanium alloy surface. The particles released into the phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) solution during the tribological tests were analysed using particle analysis and statistically evaluated.

2. Experimental

2.1. Preparing and characterisation of the coatings

The surfaces of powder-metallurgy prepared β -Ti39Nb alloy (22*20*4 mm) and cast $\alpha + \beta$ -Ti-6Al-4 V alloy (ϕ 15 mm, 2.6 mm thickness) were mechanically modified to unify the surfaces using a vibratory finishing machine (OTEC, Germany) for 24 h using stainless

steel media (satellites, 3/5 mm). The β -TiNb (61/39) PVD layer was deposited on $\alpha + \beta$ -Ti-6Al-4 V alloy in the Hauzer Flexicoat 850 (Hauzer, Netherlands) PVD unit based on magnetron sputtering method (Table 1). Samples of $\alpha + \beta$ alloy with PVD layer (PVD-Ti39Nb) and β alloy (TiNb) were modified using MAO technique for 15 min (PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min, Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min) and 45 min (PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min, Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min) at electrolyte composition and process conditions of MAO process presented in previous work [12]. The process flow is shown in Fig. 1.

The structure and chemical composition of the sample surfaces were analysed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) JEOL JSM-7610F-Plus (JEOL, Japan) equipped with an energy dispersive spectrometer (EDX, Oxford Instruments). The thicknesses of the MAO coatings were evaluated in cross-section with SEM using a backscattered electron (BSE) detector and the thickness of the deposited TiNb layers were measured using a KSG 110 Calotest device (INOVAP, Germany). The surface morphology was imaged in semi-contact mode of an atomic force microscope (AFM, LiteScope™, Czech Republic) to provide a correlative analysis between AFM/SEM. Surface roughness parameters R_a , R_z were measured with a Talysurf 50 contact profilometer (Taylor Hobson, England). The chemical states of the elements present were determined by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). The XPS spectra were collected by hemispherical analyser using Al K_{α} radiation source. Charge shift of spectra was corrected by setting up of binding energy position of adventitious carbon peak at 284.5 eV. The phase structure of the MAO coatings was identified by powder X-ray diffractometry (XRPD) using the Rigaku Ultima IV diffractometer (Japan) equipped with a scintillation detector. Measurements were carried out: reflection mode, working conditions Cu K_{α} radiation - 40 kV, 40 mA; K-beta filter; CBO selection slit - BB; Scan speed / Duration time - 1°/min; Step width - 0.02°; Scan range 10–100°2 θ ; Incident and receiving slit 1–2/3°; Receiving slit 2–0.6 mm. The phase composition was evaluated using ICDD PDF-22022 database.

2.2. Tribological and adhesion analysis

The tribological properties were tested using the TRB-S-CE-0000 tribometer (CSM Instruments, Switzerland) in a ball-on-disk arrangement. An Al_2O_3 ball with a diameter of 6 mm was used as a friction counterpart. Both the sample and the ball were cleaned with acetone prior to testing; the tests were performed in (PBS) to simulate the environment of the human body. The solution was prepared by dissolving a Sigma-Aldrich PBS tablet in 200 ml of distilled water and contained 10 mM phosphate buffer, 2.7 mM KCl, and 137.0 mM NaCl with pH 7.4 at 25 °C. The solutions containing the wear particles were collected for further analysis after the tests.

During tribological tests, the normal load of 1 N was used, and the linear sliding speed was set to 50 $\text{mm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. The tests were carried out twice on each sample; the number of laps for each test was 5000. The coefficient of friction μ was calculated from the ratio of the tangential friction force and the normal force. The surfaces of the Al_2O_3 ball and the wear track, as well as the width of the wear track, were analysed using a digital microscope DSX1000 (Olympus, Japan) after the test. The wear track profile was also analysed using a NewView 7200 optical

Table 1
Deposition parameters.

Parameters	Ti39Nb
Target	61% Ti / 39% Nb
Coating pressure (mbar)	$3.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Temperature (°C)	250
Gas	Ar
Gas Flow (sccm)	90
Deposition time (min)	180
Power mode (kW)	5
Voltage bias (V)	0

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of sample preparation.

profilometer (Zygo, USA) and a Talysurf Series 2 contact profilometer (Taylor-Hobson). The wear rate was calculated from the equation $k = V/Fs$ (Archard, 1953), where k is the wear rate, V is the wear volume, F is the normal load, and s is the sliding distance. The wear volume was obtained by multiplying the area of the wear track cross-section and its circumference.

Adhesion tests were performed with the Revetest Scratch Xpress+ scratch tester (CSM Instruments, Switzerland). A Rockwell diamond tip (radius 200 μm) was used as an indenter. The scratch test load was set to increase linearly from 1 N to 20 N along the 2 mm scratch path with a linear speed of 10 $\text{mm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$.

2.3. Electrochemical tests

The corrosion properties of the substrates and oxide layers were evaluated using potentiodynamic polarisation (PDP) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). All electrochemical tests were performed using the electrochemical workstation PGZ 100 (VoltaLab, United Kingdom) in a three-electrode setup. The sample was connected as a working electrode, a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) was set as a reference electrode, and a high-purity carbon rod was connected as an auxiliary electrode. The tests were performed in an isotonic physiological solution (0.9 wt% sodium chloride in demineralised water) to simulate the living body environment. Before starting the potentiodynamic polarisation, the initial potential value was set to -70 mV vs the open circuit potential (OCP) after stabilisation of the corrosion equilibrium, with the polarisation rate set to 1 $\text{mV}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$.

2.4. Particle and statistical analysis

The PBS solutions with particles from the tribological tests were filtered using a vacuum filtration apparatus with 100 nm pore size membrane filters (WhatmanTM, USA). The filters with deposited particles were dried for 4 h at 105 ± 0.5 °C. The filters prepared in this way were analysed using the AZtecFeature particle analysis technique (Oxford Instruments), which allows individual particles to be evaluated in terms of a combination of morphological and chemical data.

The AZtecFeature software identified all background particles using the grey level threshold of the image, which was obtained using the contrast in the images taken by BSE. Morphological and chemical analysis was performed by SEM/EDX on all particles detected by the set threshold with particle sizes >1 μm and output energies $>20,000$ counts. The analysis was performed at three different filter locations with a single analysis area of 46.27 mm^2 , 120 windows at $150\times$ magnification and 5% window overlap. The morphological parameters evaluated included equivalent circular diameter (ECD) and area.

The resulting values of the roughness parameters (R_a , R_z) for each sample were compared using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's test at statistical significance $p < 0.01$ using Minitab[®] 17 statistical software. Results were presented as mean \pm standard deviation (S.D.).

A multivariate approach was also applied to assess the general trends in the data. Principal component analysis was used to analyse the relationships between the samples and all original variables; multiple factor analysis was used to analyse the relationships between are, ECD, material, time and grouped variables – tribological variables and particle composition. Prior to the analysis, the data on particle composition was subjected to centred-log-ratio transformation allowing proper analysis of a correlation matrix while enabling the identification of the variables analysed. All analyses were performed in the R environment, namely using the FactoMineR package.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Surfaces and chemical analysis

The resulting topography of the sample surfaces (Fig. 2) shows their different behaviour depending on the treatment method used and the applied process conditions. The surfaces of the cast $\alpha + \beta$ Ti6Al4V and β -Ti39Nb alloy prepared by powder metallurgy show (Fig. 2) in 2D and 3D views the presence of tool marks. In the case of the Ti39Nb PVD layer, a smooth, dense surface without structural defects was observed (Fig. 1). The application of MAO is well known in terms of the formation of a dense porous structure with “craters” present, which were observed in correlative 3D imaging on all MAO coatings (Fig. 2). The evolution of the porous structure related to the discharge time (15 min, 45 min) on the sample surface and the appearance of different surface topography with the presence of a more significantly represented “crater” porous structure (Supplementary Fig. S1). The intensity of the oxide layer and the time required for the formation of the oxide layer involves the formation of different-sized micropores and craters observable on the sample surface, where the melt is displaced by the discharge channels and the subsequent rapid solidification in the electrolyte environment [20]. The discharge channels, following rapid solidification, presented an inhomogeneous surface microstructure, which in turn affected the resulting increase in surface roughness.

Surface morphology was evaluated for all samples using the roughness parameters R_a , R_z . The results in Table 2 confirm that in addition to the chosen electrolyte composition and concentration [21], the process time has a statistically significant effect on the surface roughness. This fact is related to the increase in the thickness of the porous oxide layer, the size of the discharge channels and the increased presence of pores, which can be eliminated by using selected additives such as polyethylene glycol [22] or glycerol [23]. Statistically significantly identical values of the roughness parameters (R_a , R_z) were determined in the case of the morphology of MAO samples Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min and PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min. Similarly, statistical agreement of the R_z parameter was achieved for the Ti39Nb input sample compared to the PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min and Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min samples.

From the results of the thicknesses shown in Table 2, which were determined by SEM from the cross section (Fig. 3), it can be concluded that the thickness of the porous oxide layer increased as the time was increased to 45 min of the MAO process, which also affected the roughness parameters. The increase in the layer thickness corresponds to the total expired charge in the present microstructure, which appeared in the range of 320–340 V. During the MAO process, the electrical resistivity of the oxide layer increases, which is related to its growth and the closure of individual discharge channels by the rapidly solidifying melt of the substrate and the ions present from the electrolyte. This fact has been well described in several works [24,25], where it was confirmed that the biologically important element Si contained in the solution was mainly determined in the outer regions of the coating; in particular, it was localised in the pore regions and their surroundings.

Fig. 2. 3D correlative probe and electron microscopy views: (a) Substrate (Ti6Al4V), (b) Ti39Nb, (c) PVD-Ti39Nb, (d) PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min, (e) PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min, (f) Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min, (g) Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min.

Table 2

Surface roughness and thickness of samples.

Sample	Roughness (μm)		Thickness (μm)	
	R_a	R_z	MAO-coating	PVD-coating
Substrate	0.09 ± 0.02	0.31 ± 0.03		
Ti39Nb	0.73 ± 0.03	6.08 ± 0.03		
PVD-Ti39Nb	0.16 ± 0.01	1.25 ± 0.09		2.8 ± 0.2
PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min	0.91 ± 0.02	6.65 ± 0.17	8.3 ± 1.2	–
PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min	2.07 ± 0.04	14.45 ± 0.50	11.5 ± 1.2	–
Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min	0.91 ± 0.01	6.32 ± 0.08	7.0 ± 0.5	–
Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min	2.77 ± 0.02	20.03 ± 0.93	12.9 ± 1.2	–

Table 3

Chemical analysis of surfaces by EDX.

Test	wt%			
	O	Si	Ti	Nb
PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min	59.6 ± 0.3	17.9 ± 0.1	16.4 ± 0.1	6.0 ± 0.2
PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min	62.7 ± 0.2	21.3 ± 0.1	12.7 ± 0.1	3.1 ± 0.1
Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min	67.3 ± 0.2	18.5 ± 0.1	9.3 ± 0.1	4.7 ± 0.1
Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min	68.1 ± 0.2	19.8 ± 0.1	8.4 ± 0.1	3.5 ± 0.1

Elemental mapping confirms (Supplementary Fig. S2) that during the MAO process, the volume of the oxide layer of the substrate material increased mainly with the incorporation of SiO_3^{2-} into the surface of the MAO layer. The PVD layer of TiNb is visible in Supplementary Fig. S2, confirming the desirable effect of eliminating the alloying elements Al and V in the layer.

Based on the XPS analysis, the elements C, O, Ti, Na, Nb, and Si and their chemical states were identified in the individual spectra (Supplementary Fig. S3). The binding energy of photoemission peaks was affected by charging of the samples which led to the shift of the spectra to higher binding energies. This shift occurred mainly for samples exposed to longer MAO process time. The charge shift was corrected using the binding energy position of C 1 s adventitious carbon peak at 284.5 eV (C–C bond). The other peaks at 282.4 and 288.0 eV energies were attributed to Si–C and O–C=O bonds, respectively [26]. The last component was observed only in the case of the longer MAO process. The presence of carbon species can be explained by possible contamination of the surfaces, but also by their presence from the glycerol-containing electrolyte to reduce the size and number of pores present [21]. The chemical state of the surface layer of the base Ti39Nb material can be characterised by Ti 2p and Nb 3d spectra (Supplementary Fig. S3). Ti 2p spectra were decomposed into two components at 456.4 and 458.2 eV corresponding to Ti^{3+} and Ti^{4+} oxidation states [27]. Nb 3d spectra are formed by one doublet at 204.8 eV, which probably corresponds to any higher oxidation state of Nb (Nb^{x+}). Due to the very low intensity of the spectra, the charging effect mentioned above and the relatively broad form of the doublet the more precise analysis of Nb oxidation state is very difficult. The other Si and Na elements present in the surface layer are due to the MAO process. Si 2p spectra taken on samples treated for 15 min were composed of two peaks at 102.8 and 100.6 eV corresponding to SiO_2 and SiC compounds [27]. After the longer treatment, an additional component at 106.3 eV appeared in the spectrum, which can be attributed to Si-C-O and/or Si-C-OH bonding. Na 1 s spectra are composed of an elemental peak at 1070.7 eV and an additional peak at 1072.7 eV, which can be attributed to the Na_2O phase

Fig. 3. BSE images of cross-sections of MAO coating (a) PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min, (b) PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min, (c) Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min, (d) Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min.

Table 3 shows the results of the EDX analysis, confirming the influence of the MAO process time, especially the higher Si content incorporated into the oxide layer after a process time of 45 min.

[28]. After the longer MAO process, a peak at a higher binding energy of 1073.8 eV was observed, which can be attributed to Na-C-OH bonding, as aforementioned. The deconvolution of O 1s photoemission spectra is based on the previously discussed interpretation. The peaks at 530.5 and 532.6 eV are due to the presence of TiO_2 , Nb_xO_y and SiO_2 oxides in the sample surface layer. The additional peak at 535.6 eV observed for samples with a longer MAO process corresponds to O-C=O bonds.

The results of XRD analysis (Fig. 4) of the MAO coatings confirmed the presence of TiO_2 in the metastable anatase phase (PDF card No. 21–1272) and the high-temperature stable rutile phase (PDF card No. 21–1276). MAO coatings of the bulk material and PVD TiNb layers showed the presence of the oxide phase $\text{Nb}_{0.94}\text{O}_{0.06}$ (PDF Card No.: 01–074-6000) and the tetragonal phase NbO_2 (PDF Card No.: 043–1043) on individual records. In the case of the PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO sample after 45 min, the high-temperature form of SiO_2 (PDF Card No.: 01–077-8310) was observed, in contrast to the other MAO coatings where SiO_2 was found in its amorphous form. The identified phases are thus correlated with the results of XPS analysis and elemental mapping.

3.2. Tribology properties

The friction coefficient and the wear rate of the samples were tested in PBS using the pin-on-disc tribometer, where the Al_2O_3 ball was the friction counterpart. In the first step, the friction coefficient was tested on the bulk materials Ti39Nb and Ti6Al4V and the Ti39Nb layer deposited on Ti6Al4V (Fig. 5a). In the second step, the friction coefficient was tested on the bulk Ti39Nb and the Ti39Nb layer, both after 15 and 45 min of MAO treatment (Fig. 5b). The friction mechanism was determined from ball wear in Figs. 6,7. After a significant running-in phase, the coefficient of friction for all MAO samples was very stable, and the abrasive wear caused by the removal of hard particles from the surface predominated [29]. The average friction coefficient of the bulk Ti39Nb samples with MAO was very similar and ranged from 0.4 to 0.5. The friction of the samples where MAO treatment was performed on the Ti39Nb layer was slightly higher and averaged in the range of 0.5–0.6. For the bulk Ti39Nb and Ti6Al4V samples, the course of the friction coefficient was less stable, and the running-in phase was significantly shorter than for samples after MAO treatment. In the case of untreated samples, the combination of adhesive and abrasive wear typical for Ti alloys was predominant [30]. The Ti39Nb sample exhibited a relatively

high coefficient of friction ($\text{CoF} > 1$), and MAO treatment effectively reduced the friction for Ti39Nb.

During the very short running-in phase, the Al_2O_3 ball penetrated the Ti39Nb coating, while friction only occurred between the Al_2O_3 ball and the Ti6Al4V base material. This was confirmed by the depth of the wear track profile (Fig. 8b), which was greater than the thickness of the Ti39Nb coating (Table 2). A friction test was performed to compare an Al_2O_3 ball and a Ti6Al4V base material (Fig. 5a), and the average friction coefficients were the similar in both cases.

The PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min and Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min samples exhibited significantly lower wear than the Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min and PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min samples. This can be attributed to the higher surface roughness after a longer MAO process (Table 2). The Ti39Nb sample showed the greatest wear when the MAO samples were compared with the untreated samples of the base materials. On the contrary, the Ti6Al4V sample showed relatively low wear (Table 4), which corresponds to the values from the previous publication [23]. MAO treatment improved wear resistance, eliminated adhesive wear, and reduced abrasive wear due to its higher hardness compared to untreated alloys [30].

The adhesion of MAO coatings was determined using the scratch test method for critical loads (L_c) from 1 N to 20 N. The adhesion of PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min and Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min (Supplementary Fig. S4) samples was without cohesion or adhesion failure. The adhesion of the PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min and Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min (Supplementary Fig. S4) samples failed after the applied force reached roughly 10.5 N, respectively 8 N. These results demonstrate that the use of the MAO process on PVD-coated Ti39Nb does not result in a decrease in the adhesion of the MAO coating. The superior measured adhesion of the MAO coating after a longer process time was caused by the higher thicknesses of these coatings because with increasing thickness of the MAO coating, a larger volume of metal enters into the oxidation process and the adhesion strength of the coating increases [31].

3.3. Electrochemical behaviour

The equivalent circuit, impedance spectra and impedance values were determined under the same conditions as in the work of Gabor et al. [12]. There were 20 measurements performed per frequency decade. Bode and Nyquist diagrams represent electrochemical

Fig. 4. The X-ray diffraction patterns of MAO coatings: A-TiO₂ – Anatase; R-TiO₂ – rutile; α-Ti – titanium; NbO - $\text{Nb}_{0.94}\text{O}_{0.06}$.

Fig. 5. The comparison of the friction coefficients of tested samples: a) base materials and b) after MAO treatment.

behaviour of different surface states under an aerated physiological solution environment (Fig. 9).

A nearly linear relationship of imaginary and real impedance was observed for all tested samples except the sample after PVD and 45 min MAO process. This is probably related to the different amount of electric charge stored by a relatively thick layer after 45 min of MAO due to its high dielectric effect. The real impedance element (Z_r) is directly dependent to the electric resistance of the layer itself, which, in turn, depends on the frequency of the electric current alternation. Three different equivalent circuits were found for different surface states of tested samples. The complexity of the equivalent circuits reflected the character of surface layers; there were multicomponent circuits found matching the electrochemical properties of the multi-layered surface treatment. Similar circuits were considered for the simulation of the behaviour of passivated titanium surface or even more complex surface treatment [32]. In contrast with the studies mentioned, it was found (by simulation) that the Warburg elements fit the obtained spectra more effectively than standard resistors. This was even more apparent for more porous and complex surface structures. Warburg elements represent the diffusion coefficient of charged ions across the surface layers.

Additionally, on the frequency domain, its effect on electrochemical behaviour was most significant at low frequencies (<10 Hz). Therefore the Warburg impedance can be considered for properly determining diffusion coefficient values of thin layers [33]. Diagrams related to EIS measurement suggest that single PVD surface treatment changes the character of surface charge transfer phenomena rather insignificantly compared to other combined surface treatments. High values of imaginary impedance (from Nyquist diagram) of both samples after 45 min of the MAO process indicate high thickness, complexity and significant micro and sub-micro porosity of surface layers.

Corrosion current relationship to polarisation potential is illustrated in Supplementary Fig. S5. Common corrosion parameters were determined by Tafel extrapolation and the Stern-Geary method from the curves. All surfaces were inspected by SEM after the corrosion tests. The PVD-Ti39Nb sample surface showed signs of pitting corrosion initiation. The area of corrosion damage and EDX spectrum of the corrosion product is illustrated in Supplementary Fig. S6.

Corrosion parameters (Table 5) of the non-treated sample were comparable and in accordance with other studies performed on Nb alloyed titanium-based materials [34]. In comparison to the other tested samples, the PVD-Ti39Nb showed the most significant shift of corrosion potential to more negative values. The different relation between the time of the MAO process and corrosion potential was hereby confirmed. While the shorter time (15 min) of MAO-treated samples resulted in the formation of a layer with more noble corrosion potential than after the longer time (45 min), samples without the MAO process showed an

opposite trend. This indicates different oxidation state of Ti- and Nb-rich surface layers. The experiment showed that the non-treated sample with only a self-formed passive surface layer exhibited the highest values of polarisation resistance. There was a negative effect of time of the MAO process on resulting polarisation resistance observed for only the MAO-treated surfaces without PVD coating. This indicates that longer MAO process times on samples without any surface pre-treatment decreased the internal integrity of their surface layers, probably by the formation of internal structural defects on the substrate/layer interface and in the layer itself [35]. Opposite behaviour was observed for samples after PVD, where a longer MAO process resulted in higher values. The corrosion rate is calculated from the exposed surface and corrosion current density. It was found that samples with higher surface roughness due to porosity (open pores) exhibit higher corrosion rate values due to significant enlargement of the real surface exposed to a corrosion medium [36]. The corrosion rate of highly porous PVD and MAO-treated surfaces was twice or three times higher compared to samples without PVD treatment (reference Ti39Nb sample). This corresponds with previous studies focused on the development and subsequent testing of dielectric surface layers on titanium-based substrates [37]. No samples other than PVD-Ti39Nb showed any signs of pitting corrosion initiation in this range of potentials. Only PVD-Ti39Nb exhibits the surface layer breakdown at approx. 4600 mV vs SCE, which was characterised by a sudden change of polarisation curve direction and a significant increase in current density [38]. Longer times of microarc oxidation treatment produced surfaces with higher corrosion rate. On the other hand the effect of treatment time did affect the polarisation resistance differently for PVD and non PVD samples. There was approx. double higher value of polarisation resistance measured for surface of specimen pre-treated by PVD and MAO treated for 45 min. On the opposite, higher time of MAO treatment of non PVD pretreated samples produced surfaces with lower polarisation resistance. The sample surface was subjected to SEM observation (Supplementary Fig. S8), which showed the presence of shallow corrosion pits.

The surface of the corrosion pit was covered by a mixture of oxide-based corrosion products and residues of PVD surface treatment. The surfaces of other samples were unaffected and showed no significant change in their morphology, indicating only the homogenous type of general corrosion.

3.4. Particle and statistical analysis

In the study, all particles present on the filter (analysis area of 46.27 mm²) were subjected to SEM/EDX analysis to characterise the particles in terms of morphology and chemical composition. Chemical analysis was also performed to reduce the influence of the saline particles. These

Fig. 6. Al₂O₃ ball wear (left) and wear track on the sample (right): a) Ti6Al4V, b) Ti39Nb, and c) PVD-Ti39Nb.

Fig. 7. Al_2O_3 ball wear (left) and wear track on the sample (right): a) PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min, b) PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min, c) Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min and d) Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min.

Fig. 8. Comparison of the track profiles of the samples: a) Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min with Ti39Nb, b) PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min with PVD Ti39Nb, c) Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min with Ti39Nb and d) PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min with PVD Ti39Nb.

Table 4

Track width and wear rate of tested samples.

Sample	Track width [μm]	Wear rate [$\times 10^{-4} \text{ mm}^3 \text{ N}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1}$]
Ti39Nb	1234 ± 28	53 ± 3.5
PVD-Ti39Nb	754 ± 24	9.3 ± 0.1
Ti6Al4V	609 ± 8	5.9 ± 0.7
PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min	304 ± 20	1.7 ± 0.5
PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min	376 ± 24	3 ± 0.6
Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min	276 ± 21	1.5 ± 0.2
Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min	361 ± 40	3.3 ± 1

NaCl and KCl particles were removed from the statistical analysis. The particles analysed after tribological measurements on the starting materials for the MAO process were evaluated based on the ECD parameter, which shows, using a histogram, a range of particles from about $5 \mu\text{m}$ to $6.8 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter. The obtained contrast and identification of the particles, including their chemical composition (O, Al, Ti, and Nb) is shown in Fig. 10. The resulting identified amount of particles is most significant for the PVD-Ti39Nb sample, indicating the influence of the PVD layer present on the Ti39Nb substrate. The resulting particles of this sample showed the presence of smaller particles ($5.08 \mu\text{m}$ on average) compared to Ti6Al4V and Ti39Nb samples. The maximum particle size of the PVD-Ti39Nb sample was up to $20 \mu\text{m}$ (ECD).

The particles identified after tribological tests on coating samples prepared by the MAO technique showed a significant influence of the MAO process on both the number of released particles and their size

(Fig. 11). The results of the AZtecFeature particle analysis confirm the influence of the MAO process time on the presence of the number of released particles. This factor is significant and correlates with the results of tribological tests (Table 4), where increased process time showed a negative effect regarding track width and wear rate for both types of samples. In addition, the chemical composition of the particles also confirms the effect of the MAO process, for example, in the presence of Si, the content of which increased with process time (Table 3).

Principle component analysis (PCA) performed on the ungrouped variables revealed the separation of the samples alongside the two first components: the first separating the Ti39Nb entry from the rest of the samples and the second separating the entry samples and the ones subjected to the MAO process. The first factor plane accounted for 59.94% of the total dataset inertia, which is greater than the reference value of 20.24% simulated for the dataset of equivalent size; hence it is highly significant. The variables most strongly correlated with the first dimension are all the tribological variables and Al concentration (positively) as well as Nb concentration (negatively). Area and ECD were, on the other hand, correlated strongly and positively with the second dimension. The visualisation of the PCA results is present in Fig. 12. The MAO samples that were prepared for 15 min showed similarity in terms of the monitored parameters (Fig. 12c). The parameters wear rate, track width and the chemical elements Si and Ti (Fig. 12b) have a significant weak positive correlation, but this shows that the representation of these elements in MAO coatings influenced the resulting tribological parameters observed. On the contrary, the negative correlation is shown by the presence of the elements O, Al, and Nb.

Fig. 9. Bode (a) and Nyquist (b) diagram.

Table 5
Corrosion parameters calculated by the Tafel extrapolation method.

Sample	Corrosion potential E_{cor} (mV vs SCE)	Corrosion rate C_R ($\mu\text{m}/\text{year}$)	Polarisation resistance R_p ($\text{k}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$)	Corrosion current density J_C ($\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$)
Ti39Nb	-75	1.30	180	0.159
PVD-Ti39Nb	-201	1.44	100	0.180
PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min	-105	3.16	62	0.390
PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min	122	4.18	138	0.510
Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min	55	1.57	153	0.193
Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min	-21	1.72	70	0.172

Multiple factor analysis (MFA) was also performed on the same dataset, only with tribological attributes and compositional grouped; the variable time of process was added to the dataset too. The visualisation of the results is present in Fig. 13. The analysis revealed the greatest association of the resulting composition of the particles with the tribological attributes and the original material as well as with, to a lesser extent, the time of the process. The area and ECD parameters were associated, to a degree, with the tribological attributes but not with the

composition of the particles. At the same time, the results show (Fig. 13a) that the selected substrate material is linked with the tribological properties and the resulting particle composition. In Fig. 13b, we can see that the process time factor is associated with the final particle composition (but not as much with tribological attributes).

4. Conclusions

The present study presents results from tribological and corrosion tests describing the behaviour of PVD and MAO layers on cast $\alpha + \beta$ Ti-6Al-4 V and β Ti39Nb alloy prepared by powder metallurgy. The study yields the following results:

- (1) By combining PVD and MAO techniques, oxide layers with increasing roughness parameters R_a , R_t for 45 min of the process and increasing Si content in the form of SiO_2 and SiC were prepared.
- (2) Tribological tests indicate efficient MAO treatment of the PVD-deposited layers and bulk material, with CoF reaching 0.4–0.6. The highest friction coefficient of $\text{CoF} > 1$ was determined for the Ti39Nb substrate, which was subsequently reduced by the MAO process. When a 15 min MAO process was applied, lower wear and wear rate were determined for both types of materials. On the contrary, better adhesion was determined for MAO coatings that were prepared for 45 min process due to the higher layer thickness.
- (3) The MAO treatment of Ti39Nb reduces the relatively high friction coefficient of 1.0–1.1 to values of 0.4–0.5; the wear rate was reduced by order of magnitude due to the MAO treatment of Ti39Nb. Compared to Ti6Al4V, the wear rate is similar, although

Fig. 10. Morphological and chemical analysis of sample particles (a) Ti6Al4V; (b) Ti39Nb; (c) PVD-Ti39Nb.

Fig. 11. Morphological and chemical analysis of sample particles (a) PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min; (b) Ti39Nb/MAO 15 min; (c) PVD-Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min; (d) Ti39Nb/MAO 45 min.

Fig. 12. Visualisation of the Principal component analysis results for (a) variables in dimensions 1 and 2; (b) variables in dimensions 2 and 3; (c) samples.

Fig. 13. Visualisation of the Multiple factor analysis results for a) dimensions 1 and 2 b) dimensions 2 and 3.

consistently lower, for all the MAO-treated samples. The main benefit is that the generated abrasive particles do not contain the toxic elements Al and V.

- (4) MAO layers prepared for 15 min showed a more noble corrosion potential. For the bulk Ti39Nb samples, the process time negatively affected the resulting polarisation resistance due to the increase in the surface defects in the MAO coating.
- (5) MAO-treated surfaces without previous PVD pre-treatment showed a corrosion rate comparable to the untreated surfaces of Ti-39Nb alloy. However, the corrosion rate of surfaces after both PVD pre-treatment and MAO was elevated due to the high level of micro/nano porosity, which increased the free surface and thus increased the corrosion rate, which was measured for standard surface area.
- (6) Novel statistical assessment based on properly transformed compositional data revealed association of the original material with both the tribological properties and the composition of the resulting particles while the process time was linked only to the particle composition.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Roman Gabor: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Project administration, Writing – original draft, Funding acquisition. **Ladislav Cvrček:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Karel Mašek:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Josef Hlinka:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Oldrich Motyka:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Validation, Writing – original draft. **Jan Walter:** Methodology, Investigation. **Grażyna Simha Martynková:** Methodology, Investigation. **Gabriela Mikesková:** Investigation, Visualization. **Jana Seidlerová:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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